

This equation turns the true price into the truest price using a golden ratio, and this is an equation that I am not able to monetise due to the total denial in Australia, because success just is NOT allowed.

TITLE>"The final price">.

Go>if>sold>then>initiate>the>linguistics>based>equation>for>the>price>sold>as>shown>where>it>starts>as>this>go>if>1.\$amount>then>multiply>the>1.\$amount>with>0.01>which>equals>2.\$amount>stop.

Go>charge>2.\$amount>shown>as>a>fee>and>send>the>2.\$amount>to>the>bank>account>with>the>BSB>of>114-879>and>the>account>number>of>419850717>and>where>the>name>of>the>account>holder>is>Lachlan>Madden>stop.

Go>if>1.\$amount>then>multiply>the>1.\$amount>with>0.91>which>equals>the>3.\$amount>stop.

Go>if>3.\$amount>then>multiply>the>3.\$amount>with>0.91>which>equals>the>4.\$amount>stop.

Go>if>4.\$amount>then>multiply>the>4.\$amount>with>0.91>which>equals>the>5.\$amount>stop.

Go>if>3.\$amount>then>add>the>4.\$amount>with>the>3.\$amount>which>equals>the>6.\$amount>stop.

Go>if>5.\$amount>then>add>the>4.\$amount>with>the>5.\$amount>which>equals>the>7.\$amount>stop.

Go>if>6.\$amount>then>subtract>the>7.\$amount>with>the>6.\$amount>which>equals>the>8.\$amount>stop.

Go>if>8.\$amount>then>proceed>to>go>and>use>the>original>1.\$amount>and>subtract>the>8.\$amount>from>the>1.\$amount>which>equals>the>price>sold>stop.

So, if you would like to allow me to put this equation on your transaction system, please call 0422 342 819.